

Environmental Persistence and Sterility in US Healthcare Settings: Insights on *Candida auris* and *Clostridioides difficile*

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Abstract

Hospital-acquired infections are of critical public health concern, leading to prolonged hospital stays, increased healthcare costs, and high morbidity and mortality rates. In the United States, pathogens such as *Candida auris* and *Clostridioides difficile* present unique challenges due to their remarkable environmental persistence. These organisms can survive on surfaces and medical equipment for extended periods, resist standard disinfectants, and contribute to recurrent outbreaks in healthcare settings. Their persistence not only sustains transmission within hospitals but also poses risks to the broader community through the potential spread of multidrug-resistant pathogens. This article analyses the role of environmental sterility in preventing and controlling infections in healthcare settings, with a focus on the challenges posed by *C. auris* and *C. difficile*. Current cleaning and disinfection strategies are reviewed alongside innovative approaches such as hydrogen peroxide vapor, ultraviolet subtype-C light, and advanced sporicidal agents. Despite the implementation of extensive infection control protocols, gaps persist in effectively addressing these pathogens, underscoring the need for strengthened environmental hygiene practices. Addressing environmental persistence is essential not only for improving patient safety in healthcare facilities but also for preventing the transmission of resistant organisms into the broader public.

Keywords: Hospital-Acquired Infections; Environmental Persistence; *Candida auris*; *Clostridioides difficile*; Healthcare-Associated Infections; Environmental Sterility; US Healthcare Setting; Infection Prevention; Disinfection Strategies

1. Introduction

Hospital-acquired infections (HAI), or nosocomial infections, are infections patients contract during medical care in healthcare settings [1]. The healthcare settings may be hospitals, long term care facilities and ambulatory settings. They also encompass occupational infections that can affect hospital staff [2]. The cause is based on the source or type of infection and the responsible pathogen, which may be bacterial, viral, or fungal.

These infections significantly threaten patient safety worldwide, leading to serious complications, longer hospital stays, higher healthcare costs, and even death [3–5]. Globally, a lot of people are impacted by nosocomial infections, but the global burden remains unknown. This is as a result of a dearth in data and surveillance systems but consistent results are seen in the United States as well as Europe [2]. In the US, the 2015 survey reported a 3.2% prevalence of HAI among hospitalized patients, notably lower than the 4% observed in a 2011 study [6]. That study also revealed that 36.4% of HAIs occurred in critical care areas, 57.5% in wards or nurseries, and 6.1% in step-down or specialty units, including mixed acuity locations with varying levels of acute care. In European hospitals, the occurrence of at least one HAI varies

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by care setting: 4.4% in primary care hospitals, 7.1% in tertiary hospitals, 19.2% in intensive care units, and 3.7% in long-term care facilities.[2] It is estimated that around 8.9 million distinct HAI episodes happen annually across acute and long-term care facilities within the European Union. The 1995 European Prevalence of Infection in Intensive Care (EPIC) study reported a 20.6% prevalence of ICU-acquired infections. [7]. The burden of nosocomial infections is greater in developing settings. A pooled analysis revealed a 15.5% prevalence, mainly as ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) and neonatal infections in intensive care units. Also, a systematic review in Southeast Asia reported an overall prevalence of 9.1% [8,9].

Environmental persistence refers to the ability of pathogens to survive and remain viable in the environment for extended periods of time. In the context of hospital-acquired infections, this phenomenon plays a critical role in the ongoing transmission and spread of harmful microorganisms, even after the immediate threat of infection has subsided. Pathogens such as *Clostridium difficile*, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), and *Candida auris* are particularly notorious for their environmental resilience, enabling them to persist on surfaces, in soil, or within water systems. This persistence poses a significant challenge to infection control efforts in healthcare settings, as these pathogens can be reintroduced into the environment and the patient population, contributing to the rise of nosocomial infections and potentially spreading to the public. The problem is further exacerbated by the fact that many of these pathogens exhibit resistance to common disinfectants and sanitizing agents, making it difficult to eradicate them completely. Environmental persistence not only leads to increased rates of infection but also prolongs hospital stays, raises healthcare costs, and in some cases, results in severe patient outcomes and deaths. Addressing this issue is crucial for improving patient safety and reducing the burden of HAIs on healthcare systems worldwide.

1.1. Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this manuscript is to examine the role of environmental sterility in the prevention and control of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) within healthcare settings in the United States. This paper will focus specifically on two pathogens that exhibit remarkable environmental persistence: *Candida auris* and *Clostridioides difficile*. These pathogens have become increasingly prevalent in US hospitals, causing significant outbreaks that are difficult to control due to their ability to survive on surfaces for extended periods, even in the presence of standard cleaning protocols.

While infection control strategies in the US have consistently targeted environmental factors, pathogens like *C. auris* and *C. difficile* pose particular challenges due to their resistance to many common disinfectants. Their ability to survive on high-touch surfaces such as bedrails, doorknobs, and medical equipment highlights the critical role of environmental sterility in infection prevention. Despite efforts to maintain environmental hygiene, the rising prevalence and persistence of these pathogens suggest gaps in current cleaning and disinfection protocols, warranting further investigation. This manuscript will analyze the environmental resilience of *C. auris* and *C. difficile*, emphasizing their resistance to standard disinfectants. For instance, *C. auris* can form biofilms on hospital surfaces, making it highly resistant to conventional cleaning agents. Likewise, *C. difficile* spores are hard to eliminate, often requiring specialized disinfectants like chlorine-based bleach or hydrogen peroxide. The paper will review existing disinfection practices in healthcare settings and explore alternative technologies, such as hydrogen peroxide vapor and UV-C light, that could enhance environmental sterility.

While the CDC acknowledges the importance of consistent and effective cleaning, challenges remain, particularly in areas with prevalent pathogens such as *C. auris* and *C. difficile*. This paper will examine the gaps identified by the CDC in environmental cleaning and the use of effective disinfectants [10].

2. Common Pathogens Exhibiting Persistence

2.1. *Candida auris*

Candida auris is an emergent fungal pathogen of particular concern. Since its first identification in Japan in 2009, it rapidly spread all over the world [11]. The main concern related to the diffusion of this fungus is its antifungal resistance. It can survive on surfaces for weeks, even when standard cleaning agents are used, and it is often resistant to multiple antifungal drugs. This toughness makes *C. auris* particularly prone to causing outbreaks in hospitals and long-term care facilities, especially in intensive care units and wards with vulnerable patients. *Candida auris*, is often multidrug-resistant yeast, has become a significant fungal pathogen due to its ability to cause invasive infections and outbreaks in healthcare facilities which have been difficult to control and treat [12].

The first six invasive isolates from three patients were also described in South Korea in 2011 in people who presented with persistent fungemia [13]. Within a decade of its discovery as a novel bloodstream pathogen, more than 4000

isolates were recovered from blood and other specimens from several countries on all inhabited continents [14–16] demonstrating how it had spread. Research have shown that once *C. auris* is introduced into a healthcare facility, it spreads rapidly among susceptible patients. So far, studies about the outbreaks of *C. auris* has been reported in the U.S., Canada, Russia, Spain, Mexico, India and some other countries [12].

C. auris frequently takes over the nares, respiratory tract, the axilla, groin and urinary tract [15,17] in hospitalized patients and has a crude mortality rate ranging from 0 to 72% in various studies [12]. *C. auris* exhibits several distinctive features, including its capacity to survive despite standard disinfectants and remain viable for months, probably because of biofilms on plastics, hospital environments, and medical devices [18,19]. Additionally, its high resistance to antibiotics such as fluconazole and inconsistent susceptibility to other azoles, amphotericin B, and echinocandins complicate the treatment of infections caused by this organism. The risk factors for the development of *C. Auris* infections are total parenteral nutrition, sepsis, longer duration of arterial or central venous catheters, ventilator support, the presence of advanced chronic kidney disease, prior antibiotic use, previous surgery, prolonged ICU stay, and multifocal colonization [20,21].

2.2. *Clostridioides difficile*

C. difficile is a gram-positive, anaerobic, spore-forming, and toxin-producing bacterium, which is also a significant cause of antibiotic-associated colitis worldwide. *C. difficile* infection ranks among the most prevalent healthcare-associated infections, easily transmitted between patients and originating from healthcare and community reservoirs. Clinical symptoms vary from asymptomatic carriage to mild diarrhea to severe conditions such as pseudomembranous colitis and toxic megacolon with septic shock. It is the leading cause of infectious diarrhea in United States hospitals and one of the most common healthcare-associated infections [22]. The cost related to *C. difficile* infection (CDI) in US acute-care facilities is estimated to be as high as 4.8 billion dollars a year [23].

The potential of *C difficile* to cause healthcare-associated outbreaks, along with high morbidity and recurrent infections, poses treatment challenges, associated costs, and, in severe cases, mortality [24]. The most significant risk factor for *C. difficile* infection is the use of antibiotics, particularly broad-spectrum antibiotics. Various antibiotic classes, including penicillins, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, and clindamycin, have been associated with the development of the disease [25]. *C. difficile* is widespread and can colonize the intestines of 3% to 5% of healthy people without causing infection. It primarily spreads through fecal-oral contact, but can also originate from environmental sources, such as soil. In healthcare settings, it's more often transmitted through contaminated surfaces and medical equipment, especially in the form of spores. These surfaces can serve as reservoirs for *C. difficile* spores, which can infect patients if infection control measures, including proper cleaning, are not followed. Healthcare environments are particularly susceptible to *C. difficile* transmission due to the difficulty of eradicating spores and the widespread use of antibiotics that promote infection development. While *C. difficile* infections have traditionally been linked to healthcare facilities, recent data show an increase in community-acquired cases among individuals without healthcare exposure to antibiotics [26].

3. Environmental Sterility Implications for Infection Prevention and Control

A great deal remains unknown about hospital-acquired infections, particularly the recently emerged *C. auris*, underscoring the urgent need for advanced resources to prevent, control, and treat these infections. *Clostridioides difficile* causes more healthcare-associated infections in the US than any other pathogen, with about 500,000 cases and 29,000 deaths annually [27]. Initially identified as a healthcare-associated pathogen, *C. difficile* infections are now more frequently acquired in the community. A better understanding of *C. difficile*'s epidemiology is decisive for developing effective infection prevention strategies in healthcare environments and the community. The emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains has made the treatment of *S. aureus* infections also increasingly challenging [28]. Unlike other yeasts that cause diseases, *C. auris* can persist on surfaces for extended periods, resist many standard disinfectants, spread easily, and is frequently multidrug-resistant [29]. As healthcare facilities advance in patient care management, keeping a clean and safe environment remains crucial. The rise of multidrug-resistant pathogens, such as *Candida auris* and *Clostridioides difficile*, has made hospital-acquired infections a significant global public health concern. These infections are complex and can spread rapidly within healthcare settings, requiring strict infection prevention measures. Such protocols not only protect patients but also prevent resistant pathogens from transmitting into the broader community. Thus, it is crucial to assess the effectiveness of infection control strategies, particularly those targeting the hospital environment, in preventing the discussed HAIs and protecting public health.

Strict environmental hygiene is crucial for preventing and controlling nosocomial infections. Contaminated hospital surfaces serve as major reservoirs and sources of dangerous microorganisms such as *Clostridium difficile* and

Staphylococcus aureus. Both porous surfaces (such as beds, mattresses, and linen) and nonporous surfaces (including bed rails, door handles, call bells, and light switches) are highly susceptible to microbial contamination with high-risk pathogens. Therefore, maintaining rigorous hygiene across hospital environments is vital. The goal of environmental hygiene is to reduce the microbial load on surfaces, thereby decreasing the likelihood of transferring infectious germs from objects to people and preventing cross-infection. Hospital cleaning is a complex, multi-layered process that involves physically removing contagious materials such as sputum, urine, blood, secretions, excretions, microorganisms, and dust using detergents, disinfectants, and water, which can support microbial growth [30].

The US Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the Healthcare Infection Control Practices Advisory Committee states that infection prevention and control are crucial everywhere medical care is provided, whether in large or small organizations or different healthcare settings [31]. Their recommendation is to provide routine, thorough cleaning of all hospital areas, both inpatient and outpatient, to help prevent the spread of infectious diseases. Hospital cleaning products often contain around 275 different ingredients and come in various forms like sprays, liquids, powders, and gases. Users need to understand the level and purpose of cleaning, including important terms such as sterilization, disinfection, and cleaning, as well as which surfaces and devices need specific procedures. For sterilization, ethylene oxide gas is used to kill all microorganisms, while disinfection has been shown to remove most active microbes except for spores [32]. Hydrogen peroxide (7.5%) is commonly used for high-level disinfection, and isopropyl alcohol at 70–90% concentration provides intermediate-level disinfection by eliminating most bacteria, fungi, and viruses. Quaternary ammonium solutions can achieve low-level disinfection by reducing most bacteria, some fungi, and viruses, but they do not eliminate spores [33]. Cleaning involves removing dirt, dust, and biological material from surfaces using brushes, scrubbing, detergents, surfactants, or water. This process helps reduce the number of contagious microbes, making it an essential first step in maintaining hospital hygiene and supporting the effectiveness of disinfection efforts [34].

4. Cleaning and Disinfection of Environment and Reusable Equipment for *Candida auris*

Cleaning surfaces two to three times daily in rooms occupied by *C. auris*-positive patients with chlorine-based or other sporicidal disinfectants has proven highly effective in controlling environmental contamination and reducing cross-transmission [35]. Reports from outbreak settings show that such interventions, when combined with staff compliance and surveillance, can halt the spread of *C. auris* within intensive care units and long-term care facilities [36]. To avoid laborious cleaning procedures and potential lapses, single-use items (e.g., pillows, bedding materials, and fiber cloth wipes for cleaning) and equipment (e.g., thermometers, blood pressure cuffs) are preferred for *C. auris*-positive patients. Low-cost items that cannot be easily cleaned should be discarded to prevent them from becoming reservoirs for the organism [35,36].

Considering that biocidal agents effective against *C. auris* must act rapidly since real-world contact times for disinfectants rarely exceed 1 to 2 minutes, commonly used hospital agents such as chlorhexidine and benzalkonium chloride demonstrate limited activity against *C. auris* [37,38]. Instead, chlorine-based products such as sodium hypochlorite (≥ 1000 parts per million, ppm) have been shown to be effective against planktonic *C. auris* cells, achieving $>6 \log_{10}$ CFU reductions within 5 minutes [39,40]. At higher concentrations (≥ 4000 ppm), sodium hypochlorite achieves similar reductions in as little as 1 minute, making it suitable for high-turnover hospital environments [40]. However, at concentrations above 6000 ppm, sodium hypochlorite may irritate patients and healthcare workers and is corrosive to certain medical equipment [38,40]. For particularly resistant biofilms, peracetic acid and sodium dichloroisocyanurate remain highly effective, preventing the regrowth and transfer of *C. auris* [41]. Alternative technologies such as hydrogen peroxide vapor and ultraviolet subtype-C (UV-C) light have been successfully employed for terminal decontamination. Hydrogen peroxide vapor achieved 96.6–100% eradication of *C. auris* on environmental surfaces within 3–5 minutes [39]. UV-C light at 254 nm has also been shown to produce $>6 \log_{10}$ CFU reductions in 30 minutes. However, its effectiveness is lower in shaded areas [42,43]. Moreover, flushing patient room sinks with ozonated water (2.5 ppm) every 4 hours has resulted in complete elimination of *C. auris* in as little as 2 days [44]. Silver nanoparticles, though still under investigation, have emerged as promising antifungal agents against *C. auris* growth and biofilm formation [118]. Terminal cleaning and disinfection of all items and surfaces in patient rooms upon discharge is mandatory, utilizing agents with certified antifungal activity. To enhance efficacy, additional measures such as fogging with hydrogen peroxide vapor, ozone treatment, and UV-C disinfection are recommended [35]. Regular environmental sampling for *C. auris* growth is essential to monitor and verify the adequacy of disinfection protocols and prevent recontamination [35].

5. Cleaning and Disinfection of Environment and Reusable Equipment for *Clostridium Difficile*

Disinfectants containing chlorine, such as diluted commercial-grade bleach, have long been trusted for thoroughly cleaning patient rooms affected by *Clostridium difficile* infection, and they work effectively [45]. These disinfectants can kill *C. difficile* spores, which are tough and resistant to many other disinfectants. However, the downside to using bleach frequently on surfaces in high-touch patient areas is that it can cause wear and tear, making daily use difficult because it can damage surfaces and cause corrosion [46]. These innovative options, such as formulations with hydrogen peroxide or peroxyacetic acid, have demonstrated excellent ability to kill spores and are effective against a variety of healthcare-associated pathogens, including *C. difficile* [38]. Due to their broad effectiveness, rapid action, and safety in hospital environments, these newer disinfectants have gained popularity in healthcare settings.

Since hydrogen peroxide and peroxyacetic acid formulations have proven effective in quickly eliminating *C. difficile* spores, they are often preferred over chlorine-based products, which can cause surface damage. These formulations significantly reduce environmental contamination in patient rooms, thereby protecting other patients and healthcare workers from potential transmission [38]. Although in vitro studies indicate that *C. difficile* spores are relatively resistant to UV light, some hospitals utilizing UV-C technology have reported improvements in infection rates in areas with high infection levels [47]. However, recent research suggests that UV-C light may not be as effective in reducing infections in endemic settings. An extensive study involving over 25,000 room cleanings found that adding UV light to cleaning routines did not lower infection rates, and in some cases, the rates were higher in rooms treated with UV [48]. Also, surfaces that patients frequently touch showed no significant drops in contamination by bacteria like *E. coli* or *Staphylococcus aureus*, indicating that relying solely on UV-C light might not be enough to control *C. difficile* spread [48]. On the other hand, the application of hydrogen peroxide vapor for terminal disinfection of *Clostridioides difficile* infection patient rooms has been correlated with a reduction in HO-CDI rates. However, these studies have not comprehensively addressed potential confounders such as patient demographics and concurrent infection control measures [49]. The efficacy of hydrogen peroxide vapor in terminal disinfection demonstrates promise; nevertheless, its implementation may be hindered by logistical challenges, particularly in non-isolation rooms or during routine daily cleaning of high-touch surfaces. Despite these logistical constraints, hydrogen peroxide vapor remains a valuable adjunct to standard cleaning protocols for mitigating *C. difficile* contamination within isolation environments.

Recommendations

To combat the increasing threat of persistent pathogens like *Candida auris* and *Clostridioides difficile* in healthcare environments, a comprehensive, multi-faceted approach is essential. Relying solely on traditional cleaning methods is no longer enough; instead, healthcare facilities should adopt enhanced disinfection strategies that integrate proven techniques with innovative technologies to achieve greater environmental sterility. Hospitals and long-term care homes should prioritize the use of sporicidal agents such as sodium hypochlorite, peracetic acid, and hydrogen peroxide-based solutions. These have proven more effective against resilient biofilm-forming and spore-producing organisms like *C. auris* and *C. difficile*, which resist standard disinfectants. Cleaning frequency, especially in high-touch areas like bed rails, medical devices, doorknobs, and call buttons, should be increased to two or three times daily during outbreaks or in contaminated zones. Furthermore, thorough terminal cleaning of patient rooms post-discharge should be performed with high-level disinfectants, paying close attention to all surfaces and reusable equipment.

Advanced disinfection technologies, including hydrogen peroxide vapor, ultraviolet-C (UV-C) light, and ozone treatment, should complement manual cleaning. These methods are effective in targeting residual microbial contamination, especially in hard-to-reach spots. Hydrogen peroxide vapor, for instance, has demonstrated success in eradicating *C. auris* and reducing *C. difficile* spores. However, deploying these systems requires careful planning to address logistical issues like room downtime and staff training. Healthcare facilities should also consider switching to single-use medical devices and consumables whenever possible particularly for patients colonized or infected with multidrug-resistant organisms. These items lower contamination risk and bypass complex sterilization, which is prone to errors. For reusable equipment, strict sterilization and reprocessing protocols must be enforced, alongside regular environmental monitoring to evaluate cleaning effectiveness. Equally vital is ongoing education and training for healthcare workers. Staff should understand the role of environmental contamination in hospital-acquired infections and be trained in proper disinfectant use, and cleaning techniques. Regular audits and feedback should be used to ensure adherence to infection control protocols. Cultivating a culture of accountability and shared responsibility within healthcare teams enhances compliance and reduces human errors.

Finally, policymakers and healthcare administrators should invest in research on new antimicrobial surfaces, coatings, and disinfectants to keep pace with evolving pathogens. Collaboration among healthcare providers, regulators, and industry is vital to foster innovation and ensure effective deployment of new solutions in clinical settings.

6. Conclusion

Hospital-acquired infections from resilient pathogens like *Candida auris* and *Clostridioides difficile* pose a serious challenge to healthcare systems globally. Their ability to survive on surfaces for long durations and resist standard disinfectants weakens infection control efforts, leading to increased patient morbidity and mortality, longer hospital stays, and higher costs. This highlights the vital role of environmental sterility in infection prevention and control. Despite ongoing cleanliness initiatives, the stubborn persistence of these organisms exposes gaps in current disinfection protocols. Addressing these gaps requires reevaluating and enhancing cleaning practices by adopting advanced technologies and sporicidal agents proven effective against these hardy pathogens. Additionally, healthcare workers' adherence to strict hygiene standards and ongoing education are crucial, as human factors significantly impact infection control success.

Going forward, healthcare facilities must implement a comprehensive, multi-layered strategy that combines improved environmental hygiene, staff training, innovative technologies, and comprehensive surveillance. This integrated approach will reduce the spread of *C. auris* and *C. difficile* and help prevent the emergence of other multidrug-resistant organisms. Ultimately, bolstering environmental sterilization will enhance patient safety, decrease healthcare-associated infections and economic cost, and reduce the public health burden of nosocomial diseases.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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